

EFFECTIVE STORYTELLING IN TEACHERS' CONTEXT

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ORCID ID: 0009-0006-1177-9445***Abstract**

This article examines storytelling as an effective instructional strategy in the context of primary education, with a particular focus on teaching English to young learners. It conceptualizes storytelling as an authentic form of communication and a carrier of cultural knowledge that supports both language acquisition and cognitive development. Drawing on relevant pedagogical literature, the study outlines key criteria for selecting appropriate stories and emphasizes the importance of systematic preparation, including the use of theatrics, props, scripting, and rehearsal. Furthermore, it proposes a structured framework of pre-, during-, and post-storytelling activities designed to enhance learner engagement, comprehension, and interaction. The article argues that storytelling facilitates the development of critical thinking skills, promotes cultural awareness, and supports integrated language learning. It concludes that, when effectively implemented, storytelling serves as a powerful and versatile tool for fostering meaningful and engaging language learning experiences in the primary classroom.

Keywords: storytelling; primary education; English language teaching (ELT); young learners; language acquisition; critical thinking; cultural transmission; classroom pedagogy; learner engagement; instructional strategies.

Introduction. Storytelling is an authentic form of communication that is a part of every culture. There are many people who are famous for crafting tales, and we still read their stories today. The legendary Aesop of Ancient Greece is probably one of the most famous storytellers; his fables are still told to children to teach moral lessons.

In many cultures, storytelling is also a tradition used to communicate culture from one generation to another to the next. For example, the elder Pueblo Indians in New Mexico pass down their culture and values to the younger generation through songs and stories. Children are actively involved with the storytelling and genuinely enjoy this traditional form of communication between generations.

In fact, many schools often use storybooks and storytelling as part of an elementary (primary) school curriculum because stories teach valuable lessons and literacy to children while also entertaining them. As Pinter A. mentions, "Listening to stories is the most authentic and popular activity for children, and primary English teachers can use storytelling as additional listening practice. Children will learn new language as well as having enjoyable listening practice. Language is picked up easily because stories contain repetition which makes linguistic input more noticeable" [4, 52-53].

Stories are a carrier of culture. As Curtain H. and Dalhberg C. state, "Story or narrative, is a powerful vehicle for experiencing culture. Values and concepts of the culture that are embedded in myths and folktales can be shared through storytelling, story reading, and dramatisation" [3, 266]. Well-written stories can capture the interest and imagination of children over multiple generations. Such stories ignite learners' curiosity

and creativity while challenging them to learn new language or understand language in a new context. They particularly cater to young learners who have short attention spans and learn best through play and entertainment. When done effectively, storytelling is an enjoyable activity in which the language learning process is undetectable to children. As Slatterly M. and Willis J. point out, "Young learners acquire language unconsciously. The activities you do in class should help this kind of acquisition. Stories are the most valuable resource you have. They offer children a world of supported meaning that they can relate to" [5, 98].

Storytelling lends itself to helping students of all levels develop critical thinking skills - "the ability to analyse facts, generate and organise ideas, defend opinions, make comparisons, draw inferences, evaluate arguments, and solve problems" [2, 6]. These are important for students to develop in a primary school curriculum because they help students gain a deeper understanding of texts, including those that provide information from variety of cultures. Teachers can help students develop critical thinking skills by asking questions that require students to analyse and make inferences and by encouraging students to compare themselves and their cultures to the stories they have heard. Through this process, students can be encouraged to form their own opinions and evaluate a story for both content and delivery. When teachers encourage students to retell a story, they must also "summarise, edit and develop" the story, not just repeat the story word for word [6, 7]. Young learners also develop the ability to sift through new stories and cultural information through a process of critical reflective thinking.

Storytelling is an art or a skill that can be developed. As you develop your storytelling skills, consider

the following criteria that provide an effective storytelling experience for young learners.

Stories should: be highly predictable, be familiar to the home culture, have a high percentage of known vocabulary, include repetitive and predictable patterns, provide opportunities to apply drama and Total Physical Response (TPR), lend themselves well to use of visuals and realia to make input comprehensible [3, 8]. If stories meet these criteria, then it is possible to present an engaging storytelling experience that will keep young learners' attention and allow them to follow along in English without using their native language.

Once you have chosen the right story, the next step is to prepare to tell the story effectively. As Brewster J., Ellis G. and Girard D. point out, "...simply reading a story aloud to a class without preparation could be disastrous, with a loss of pupil attention, motivation and self-confidence. Pupils' enjoyment will increase enormously if we ensure their understanding is supported in

several ways. Pupils will also need to feel involved and relate the story to aspects of their own experience" [1, 192]. Some teachers feel anxiety over storytelling because they feel that they have no natural talent for it, or they lack confidence in their own English language skills. However, with thoughtful preparation and practice, all teachers can create a successful storytelling experience for their students.

To make your storytelling engaging, prepare these four elements: Theatrics, Props, Script, and Rehearsals.

Aim to include aspects of these four elements in every storytelling session. If this is a new concept, start small and build up your skills slowly. As you gain confidence using one aspect, add another to your repertoire. The theatrics and props are particularly important as they help to generate interest and enjoyment in learners, and make input comprehensible.

Consider the story of Cinderella.

Theatrics	Props
Gestures	Visuals for setting and characters
Body movement	Realia
Dramatic pauses	Masks for role play
Character voices	Costumes for role play
Facial expressions	Hand or finger puppets
Speaking slowly and clearly	PowerPoint slides or storyboards

STORYTELLING PREPARATION

Rehearsals	Script
Memorise the text	Use illustrations from the storybook
Use cue cards if needed	Adapt the script to learners' level
Practice in front of the mirror	Create roles students can play
Record/videotape yourself	Integrate songs or chants
Rehearse using props	Prepare places for questions and predictions
Practice, practice, practice!	

Children love to hear stories told with different character voices, so you could use a young girl's voice for Cinderella; a rough, rude voice for her stepmother, unpleasant voices of her stepsisters, etc. In addition, you could use hand puppets and a drawing of the Cinderella's house on a poster or in a PowerPoint presentation along with the character voices. The combination of voices, puppets and the background drawing would make the storytelling fun and entertaining and would also help students understand the story better. Use a variety of theatrics and props to keep each storytelling fresh and new for learners.

Another storytelling element to consider is the script, which should be carefully prepared to be just

above the learners' level of English and incorporate both new and known vocabulary and grammatical structures. Furthermore, script preparation should also build in time for student participation and comprehension questions throughout the storytelling, which will help keep the level of student engagement high. Children can role-play with the script by playing the character parts in Theatre's activities. The script can be simplified to adjust to the learners' level.

Finally, it is vitally important to rehearse the storytelling before the class. Although it is best to memorise as much of the text as possible, it can be helpful to prepare cue cards (cards with key words and plot elements from the script) to help guide your performance.

In order to design effective storytelling activities, it is important for teachers to think about activities before, during and after the storytelling. In addition to the preparation for making the story come alive, the teacher needs to prepare students with the language to understand the storytelling before. Activities to keep students active and engaged in class at every step of the storytelling should also be planned [7].

I. Activities before Storytelling.

Such activities are done to aid comprehension, create interest and enjoyment, make the storytelling more meaningful and encourage critical thinking.

Capture students' attention: use pictures to introduce the story in a fun and interesting way or you can create fun visuals. To make the characters come alive, the teacher can make stick puppets of the characters and introduce them to the class. To draw students into the scenery of the story, the teacher can make a background on poster paper and put it up on the classroom wall or project the scenes from the laptop onto the wall. For example, for the story 'The Rainbow Fish' the teacher may use an underwater scene from the book and brightly-coloured puppets of the fish and a multicoloured Rainbow Fish with shiny silver scales.

Connect to prior knowledge and experience: it is important to connect students' lives to the story. This includes introducing the main ideas, concepts or characters to students. For example, if the story is 'Goldilocks and the Three Bears', the teacher may prepare students by introducing the concepts of family since the story's main characters are Goldilocks, Baby Bear, Mama bear, Papa Bear. The teacher can also ask students about their own country or culture's since many countries have similar fairytales or folktales.

Review language students have learned: The review of language is often related to background knowledge and students' experiences.

For example, to repeat grammar structures and vocabulary, large thematic units, etc. 'The Very Hungry Caterpillar' has vocabulary for food, numbers, days of week and the life cycle of a butterfly, so the teacher may connect students' background knowledge of food with the concepts of food, numbers, etc.

Pre-teach new vocabulary and expressions: If there are key words or structures that are necessary to comprehend the story and cannot be inferred from the context, it is better to teach them before the storytelling. The teacher can capture attention, introduce the context, review known words, and then pre-teach vocabulary.

Ask students to predict what will happen in the story: It can be helpful to encourage students to predict what will happen in the story. Prediction is a good critical thinking skill to encourage students. Be sure to record their thoughts to check whether they are correct later. Students can write one sentence they think will be in the story and put it in a prediction box. Then at the end of the story, the teacher can read the sentences out loud for fun. To lower level students, the teacher can write some sentences on the board, and ask students to choose the ending by writing one of them. For example, for Aesop's fable about the Lion and the Mouse, the teacher can give these sentences for students to choose

and write: 'The Lion eats the mouse. The mouse saves the lion. The lion saves the mouse.'

Making a prediction helps students pay attention to the story and think critically to check their predictions during the storytelling.

Give students a purpose for listening: Before telling the story, give students a purpose for listening, so this can help them stay engaged and make them more active listeners during the storytelling (for example, to repeat sounds, songs, chants, lines from the story, etc).

II. Activities during Storytelling.

During storytelling activities are usually used to check comprehension. They can also be used to keep students' interest and allow them the chance to interact and practice using English.

Q & A: the teacher should keep a balance between asking questions (like, about the characters, setting, and plot) to keep the learners engaged. For example, if he is telling the Aesop's fable 'The Hare and the Tortoise' it could progress like this: "A hare is also called a ..." (rabbit); "A tortoise is also called a ..." (turtle); "What is Hare doing?" (hopping fast); "is Tortoise sleeping too?"

Repetition: repetition of key phrases or chants in a story can keep students active and give them a chance to practice set phrases or language structures.

TPR (Total Physical Response): movements and actions can be built into the most students' stories. Doing TPR with students during the storytelling appeals to kinaesthetic learners and makes the experience more active and fun [8]. This is also supports comprehension of the story and the teacher should look for movement to accompany a storytelling.

Create your own ending: Teachers can tell the story up to the climax asks students to predict the ending before they finish telling the story.

Keep ask students to predict in Warm-up.

III. Activities after Storytelling.

After a storytelling, you can do follow-up activities to check comprehension of the story. Post-storytelling activities should also give learners plenty of practice using the new language structures and vocabulary. Try to use four language skills, cooperative activities, scaffolded instruction and activities that cater to different learning styles and intelligences.

Check predictions: check the predictions that students made in the before- or during-storytelling stages.

Group retelling may include role-play; students can act out the story, etc.

Games: try the game 'Start and Stop', where you can retell the story with mistakes and have students stop you when they hear a mistake.

Story analysis: Students can show their deeper levels of comprehension of the story by analysing the characters, ending or moral of a story and plot.

Personalised story: Have student write a story similar to the one in the storytelling but with details that draw from their own experiences, culture and imagination.

Projects: Have students work together in small groups to complete a project that shows comprehension of a story. The project can be a part of a thematic unit requiring students to learn more about the story topic,

context, author, culture, etc. Student can also research information about the author.

Play performance.

Conclusions. Storytelling is a fun, exciting way to present English in a meaningful context and expose students to their culture. It is also an authentic form of communication. Storytelling can help teachers incorporate the development of critical thinking skills and deepen their understanding of how stories are connected to their lives and culture.

Since storytellers are performers, teachers can be ready to prepare their theatrics, props, script and rehearse before performing.

Good storytelling involves preparing before-, during-, and after-storytelling activities. These activities capture students' attention and encourage them to practice the language.

Moreover, storytelling can promote thematic learning that develops the four language skills in an integrated period of time.

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